

THE STRATEGIES OF DECREASING POVERTIES IN DEVELOPING COUNTRIES

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the importance of PPPs as institutional solutions to the existing poverty lines and security issues in rural areas, the problems and risks of their implementation. Based on the specifics of the regions, proposals are developed on what investment income is suitable for overcoming poverty. In general, the development of small-scale PPP experience in improving the social environment at the grassroots level, the results of foreign analysis are suitable for Uzbekistan. The article presents a comparative analysis, statistics.*

Keywords: *poverty, economic growth, inclusive economic growth, public-private partnership.*

Introduction. Although the fight against poverty is being fought in the countries of Central Asia and the results are visible, the pace of its decline in the region has slowed down. What does this indicate? It means that the projects being developed in the region, state programs and initiatives implemented by members of society may have reduced their effectiveness or that a newly formed layer is increasing. At the same time, based on the conclusions of numerous studies and data, most of these poverty indicators fall on areas where the population lives in villages and remote areas with limited employment opportunities. Based on the information provided by the World Bank on similar problems, it is emphasized that further strengthening these ideas and efforts towards sustainable development goals should be considered a priority task of the region [1].

Literature review. According to Benedict (2022), Leigland (2020), and O'Shea, since 2010, the private sector has been increasingly interested in affordable housing and infrastructure. This trend is continuing in both the West and the East. However, in most cases, this is being implemented on the basis of public-private partnerships. Liu, Beagle and Christiansen and Bapna note that while significant progress has been made in reducing poverty over the past two decades, more reforms are needed not only to further reduce extreme poverty levels, but also to reduce the number of people living in extreme poverty.

On the other hand, McKinsey argues that PPPs are seen as an alternative to development banks, economic development banks, and investment. On the other hand, critical urban studies often conceptualize PPPs as inherently problematic, framing their arguments around the conflicting goals and timelines of public and private sector actors [2].

According to the Bai, X. Dawson, R.J. Üрге-Vorsatz - The state and its organizations responsible for sustainability, as well as the private sector, must understand that social sustainability can be achieved through future agreements at the national and international policy level. In turn, those implementing these projects, while ensuring economic and social stability, are also causing ecological imbalances. Due to excessive energy consumption, it is the organizations mentioned above that are responsible for 75% of global emissions [3].

Research methodology. The study involves the use of economic analysis, statistical methods, and comparative analysis methods to study poverty levels in our countries.

Analysis and results. Since the international poverty line takes into account conditions in the world's poorest countries, it is not fully relevant for high-income countries. This indicator generally rises in monetary terms as a country's prosperity increases. As countries become wealthier, they become more powerful and set higher standards for poverty reduction. To partially fill this gap, the World Bank has supplemented the concept of the "International Poverty Indicator" by introducing a poverty classification by income. In this case, the basic approach remains the same - the income level of citizens is based on the value of the national poverty line in countries that fall into one of four groups:

1. Low-income countries (\$1,035 or less per person per year);
2. Lower-middle income (\$1,036-4,045 per year);
3. Upper-middle income (\$4,046-12,535 per year);
4. High-income (\$12,536 or more per year).

About 1.5 billion people live in absolute poverty, meaning they earn less than \$2 a day. 70% of this population are women. Women do two-thirds of the world's work, produce half of the food, but earn only 10% of the world's income. There are currently about 1 billion adults in the world who are illiterate, and two-thirds of them are women.

The United Nations uses the official term "least developed countries" to assess the level of economic development. This "black" list includes countries with a per capita GDP of less than \$750. Currently, there are 48 such countries, and it is no secret that the poorest are African countries. They are on the UN list 33rd.

Table-1. The list of poorest countries of the world [4]

#	Countries	Characteristics
1	Togo	It is a major producer of phosphorus and a leading exporter of cotton, cocoa, and coffee. The average citizen of the country has to survive on \$1.25 a day!
2	Malawi	In Malawi, the critical situation is related to IMF debts. The government is directly related to the fulfillment of its duties, which has forced the government to isolate the country from the assistance of international financial institutions. A vivid example of the inefficiency of natural resources.
3	Sierra Leone	bauxite and ordinary Sierra Leoneans do not eat more than two meals a day. A similar situation is developing in CAR, which has huge reserves of resources. The average income of the local population is one dollar.
4	Burundi	Burundi and Liberia are countries held hostage to ongoing military conflicts
5	Zimbabwe	Zimbabweans die of AIDS before they reach the age of forty.
6	Liberia	Burundi and Liberia are countries held hostage to ongoing military conflicts
7	Democratic Republic of Congo	The situation in Congo is very difficult, as diseases of the local population are accompanied by continuous military operations.

There is also a poor country located in Europe. There is a problem here. Of course, in terms of the level of development, a European country is significantly different from African countries.

According to Eurostat, the poorest countries in Europe are Bulgaria, Romania and Croatia. Over the past three to four years, Bulgaria's economic well-being has improved slightly, but the GDP level remains low (no more than 47% of the European average).

While we were looking for the current level of poverty in Uzbekistan and ways to eliminate it, we first considered it appropriate to conduct a general analysis of the situation in the region. As a result, we observed that the poverty level in the Central Asian countries has been decreasing for years and the living standards of the population of the countries are improving. For example, in Tajikistan, the situation was very sad in the early 2000s, but as a result of economic development, cooperation and government programs in the region, we observe a decrease of 23% as of the 1st quarter of this year.

Similar processes have been observed in other regions of the region, including Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan, and Kazakhstan, the country with the highest economic potential in Central Asia, where poverty rates have been declining for years. However, despite this, the rate of poverty reduction in the region has slowed down in recent years. We can attribute this to various reasons, and it would not be wrong. For example, the consequences of the global pandemic in 2020 will also have an impact on 2021-2022.

Table 2. The poverty rate in central Asian countries [5]

#	Countries	The rate of poverty by years						
		2002	2015	2019	2020	2024	2025 1 st quarter	Forecasting 2030
1.	Tajikistan	81%		13%		28%	23%	15%
2.	Kyrgyzstan	70%	5%	20%	25%		33%	
3.	Turkmenistan							47%
4.	Uzbekistan	24%		13%	12%	11%	11%	6%
5.	Kazakhstan	47%	3%	5%			5%	

The reasons for this include the fact that the population growth rate in the countries of the region is faster than the economic development rate, institutional factors in the countries, the level of literacy of the society, the level of education and employment, and even the inability of the countries of the region to be completely independent in foreign policy, and at the same time, the slowness of some parties in implementing mutual cooperation among the countries of Central Asia, and their superficial attitude towards economic unions. Of course, internal situations are more important than external situations.

Now, if we come to the situation in Uzbekistan, of course, as a representative of this region, all the above-mentioned situations also apply to us. No matter how many economic programs a country develops, no matter how much financial assistance, subsidies, and tax breaks are provided, if the views of society are not changed, their consciousness is not formed, if the level of knowledge, literacy, behavior in a business environment, honesty and hard work, and the concept of patriotism are not formed, all this work is in vain. We see this in the example of preferential loans, social assistance provided on the basis of state programs, which ensure the implementation of these reforms, but the result, that is, the effectiveness, is very low. The reason is that the poor part of society we are talking about has already suffered from the “disease of dependency”. We are witnessing this in the way of life of society. For these reasons, we conducted an analysis in which regions of Uzbekistan poverty is observed and tried to find the cause and solution to it.

Figure 1. The poverty rate by regions of Uzbekistan

In our analysis, we studied and developed a map of poverty indicators for the period 2023 and 2024. According to it, we observe that the Republic of Karakalpakstan decreased from 13.6% to 10.8%, in Andijan region from 11.9% to 9.5%, in Khorezm region from 14.1% to 11.9%, in Syrdarya region from 13.8% to 11.3%, in Namangan region from 10.4% to 7.6%, in Navoi region from 7.6% to 5.7%, and in Tashkent city from 7.9% to 7.3% (Figure 1).

Of course, these positive changes make us happy, and we know that behind the positive results there is a lot of work, including many programs, reforms, support, and international experience. But in most regions of our country, the average indicator remains at 9-10%, which means that 9-10 out of every 100 people live in poverty and destitution. In other words, this is like “waiting for their happiness under the sun”. Because these 9-10% of society members look with hope for an improvement in their way of life and want support, which is part of the problem we are talking about.

If we look closely at the numbers, we can see that the poverty rate is more consistent with rural areas, and we would like to explain this by the fact that the population in these areas has low income, is deprived of social benefits, and is unable to access high-quality education and health services, or is generally unable to do so. The additional measures we are proposing are aimed at reducing poverty in rural areas and represent the implementation and acceleration of projects based on public-private partnerships in education, healthcare, and access to social services. Because this will create the opportunity to activate domestic investments and transform labor resources into human capital, which will increase the potential of society, improve health, increase income, and increase GDP, as a result of which we will have access to social benefits.

In the healthcare sector, in recent years, we have witnessed good results from public-private partnership projects in oncology and dialysis. At the same time, PPP projects in the preschool and education system have yielded good results. As a result, the coverage of children with preschool education has increased from 30% in 2020 to 71.8% in 2025. At the same time, the coverage of 6-year-old children with the preschool preparation system has been increased to 90%.

Conclusion. It is worth noting that every year the situation in the ranking of poor countries changes. Some powers give way to others, sink or rise one or two steps, but in most cases the overall picture remains unchanged. The fight against poverty is the main task of the world community. At this point, we conclude from all the analyses that it is necessary to develop a special

form of public-private partnership mechanism in rural areas and immediately begin to apply it in the regions. We believe that it is important to form PPP projects specifically for handicrafts, taking into account the specialization of the regions. In this regard, the proposals we have developed are as follows:

- Taking into account the geographical, social formation and analytical skills of the regions, it is necessary to support PPP projects specifically for the part of society listed in the Iron Book. Local authorities, neighborhood citizens' assemblies and women's committees should be mobilized in the development of such projects;

- It is necessary to encourage the use of domestic investments in the implementation of PPP projects. In this regard, it is necessary to develop proposals for the use of regional general funds (local + private) in financing PPP projects. These proposals should be implemented by the Ministry of Economy and Finance, local financial associations, the Khokimiyat and the State Tax Inspectorate, who are responsible for developing an incentive package.

- Instead of ineffective subsidies, a small business support fund should be formed and a small business subsidy project should be launched;

- There is state support for the treatment of chronically ill members of society. However, it is advisable to ensure that this support is provided in regional hospitals, thereby ensuring that funds are retained in the region.

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